

FORMATION OF SOCIAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE EDUCATORS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the formation of the general social competence of educators. The definition of the concepts of the concept of "competence", "competence", "social competence", "professional competence" is given. The important socio-pedagogical skills and social competence of the future educator in the educational process are considered.*

Keywords: *competence, social competence, future teacher of preschool education, pedagogical competence, personal and professional self-determination.*

In the modern educational space, there is a need to train professionally competent, socially active and competitive specialists who are ready to provide society with sustainable, safe and successful development, as society puts in front of a person more and more complex tasks of self-determination and self-realization, which only free independent, socially active person.

The dynamism of the ongoing changes, new strategic guidelines in the development of the economy, politics, socio-cultural sphere objectively put forward the problem of high-quality training of professional and pedagogical personnel as a priority. Updating and changing the goals and objectives of education, the formation of new educational structures, new content of education requires new technologies for teaching teachers who are prepared for professional activities, capable of pedagogical self-determination, self-organization and self-government. An important role in the fulfillment of this task belongs to the system of professional and pedagogical education, since the teaching staff, first of all, will carry out the mission of transferring the system of professional education to a qualitatively new level. [3]. The system of vocational education is faced with the task of giving future teachers a "reserve of fundamentality" that contributes to the formation of a competent, responsible specialist who is fluent in his profession and oriented in related fields of activity, ready for constant professional growth, social and professional mobility. In the field of view of scientists are the issues of forming the ability of the future educator to self-development, mastering socio-pedagogical skills in personal and socially-oriented situations of communication, which allows students to develop the ability to social contacts, communicative interaction and communication with the outside world.

The essence of the concept of "competence". In modern conditions of increased attention of society and the state to the effectiveness and competitiveness of education in the post-Soviet space, the problem of forming the professional competence of future specialists is becoming a priority. Reforming the system of higher economic education is aimed at preparing a new generation of professionals with creative potential and a high level of IQ, capable of building an open information society focused on meeting the material and spiritual needs of people. Since for each developed state in the modern open world community the role of training such a generation of professionals who are ready for the creative realization of the economic potential of their

country is constantly increasing, this is precisely why the urgency of the problem of forming and developing the professional competence of future teachers is constantly increasing [4].

Competence (lot. "competere", ing. "competence", "competence" - "ability", "worthy"): 1. Determine the scope of authority of official or official documents; power. 2. A person's knowledge in any area of the same level in that area. 3. Effective use of theoretical knowledge to demonstrate a high level of professionalism, skill and strength.

An analysis of the scientific literature has shown that social competence consists of a body of knowledge about society and the specifics of the development of social and social relationships in it, from practical skills to apply this knowledge in educational processes, and also to develop the abilities of a socially active person in preschool children. Consequently, the socially active personality of the future educator is a creative, professionally determined, mobile, open to innovation personality.

A modern teacher-educator needs to possess a number of competencies, which together determine the level of his professionalism.

Psychological and pedagogical competence determines the level of training of a teacher of psychology and pedagogy, his ability to take into account the individual characteristics, abilities and natural gifts of preschool children and provide pedagogical support in their further development.

Methodological competence is, first of all, the formed abilities of the educator for reflective analysis, design and professionally competent conduct of classes of various target orientations.

Communicative competence is an integral component of the personal and professional characteristics of a teacher. The ability to interact with students and colleagues on a humane basis largely determines the results of personal achievements and achievements in the field of pedagogical activity.

Speech competence is a structural component of speech culture, knowledge of pronunciation, spelling, stylistic, intonational and other national and cultural, the ability to competently use this knowledge in the process of interpersonal communication; possession of such qualities of speech as clarity, clarity, persuasiveness, emotionality. Possession of speech competence allows the educator to attract the attention of students, unobtrusively force them to listen to advice, recommendations, requests, and also encourage them to take action.

Self-educational competence implies the constant readiness of the teacher to improve the level of qualifications, professional competence in various types of pedagogical activity, as well as the improvement of personal qualities that appeal to preschool children and cause a sense of respect and admiration for the teacher. Such qualities include impartiality, the ability to listen and communicate, the ability to keep one's word, goodwill, friendliness, readiness to provide support.

Sociocultural competence is a complex of knowledge about personal, business and professional ethics, business image. This knowledge and relevant skills are an indicator of the level of the teacher's communicative, personal and business culture, which manifests itself in different life situations and can be considered a guarantee of success in solving personal and professionally significant issues.

Social competence is an important component in the range of professional competence of the teacher-educator, it enables the teacher to build relationships with society: parents, public organizations, including social institutions: departments of social protection of the population, insurance companies; cultural and educational institutions [1]. Thus, it becomes obvious that the

social competence of the future educator, being formed at the theoretical level at the university, develops in the field of professional activity in conjunction with all other types of competencies.

The development of social competence is a multilevel process. At the basic level, called the professionally oriented level, future educators acquire theoretical knowledge of social pedagogy and the skills of organizing work on the personal and professional self-determination of students, taking into account the development of the social sphere of society. Of particular importance are such forms of classes as discussion, during which future educators master socio-pedagogical terminology, concepts and categories.

The second professionally advanced level of social competence is formed in the process of teaching practice and develops in the field of professional activity after graduation. Young specialists are involved in active social activities and solve professionally significant tasks by organizing group work, project and research work of students, using modern methods and socio-pedagogical technologies. At the same time, the pedagogical experience and achievements of other teachers play an important role, the presentation of which, as a rule, is carried out at methodological associations, problematic seminars, scientific and practical conferences.

The third level is characterized by the productive activity of the future educator using such forms of work as a creative workshop, which opens up the opportunity for students to independently solve practice-oriented tasks, penetrating into the area of future professional activity. Based on a solid theoretical base developed by researchers, it is possible to single out the most important social and pedagogical skills of the future educator:

- to know the individual characteristics of students, to discover and develop their talents;
- plan career guidance process on an activity basis;
- select the most appropriate social and educational technologies that are adequate to the needs and personal expectations of students;
- build social relationships and establish long-term contacts with other institutions and departments;
- to establish feedback with the parent community;
- master the art of interpersonal communication and aesthetic culture.

The main components of the social competence of the future educator are the following components:

- socio-perceptual (knowledge and understanding of people, observation and insight);
- socio-psychological (knowledge of the patterns of behavior, activities and relationships of a person included in a professional group, team, work in a team);
- auto-psychological (self-knowledge, self-esteem, self-control, the ability to manage one's condition and performance, self-efficacy);
- communicative (possession of various strategies and methods of effective communication);
- psychological and pedagogical (implementation of influence) [2].

In scientific research, there is a noticeable desire to make the process of developing the social competence of a future educator (already within the framework of postgraduate professional education) problematic, to use a more reflective approach, and to constantly monitor the results of the teacher's achievements.

The formation of the social competence of the future educator in the educational process is correlated, on the one hand, with the global goal of the educational system - the development of

the personality of the teacher. This refers to the development of his intellectual, emotional-volitional and such personal qualities as purposefulness, responsibility, humanity, tolerance, citizenship, etc. On the other hand, for the future educator, the ability to form social competence in their pupils is of fundamental importance [3].

Thus, the organization of the educational process and constant monitoring of the quality of education will contribute to increasing the level of social competence. The indicator of quality is the level of mastery of the future educator with social competence.

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